

Synthesis and properties of poly methyl methacrylate membrane in the presence of poly vinyl acetate by template polymerization

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Abstract : This communication presents the detailed study on the preparation and properties of poly methyl methacrylate membrane produced during the template polymerization in the presence of polyvinyl acetate as a template. The behaviour of poly methyl methacrylate membrane towards absorption in various solvents has been investigated which shows that the absorption of water in the membrane is highest and ethylene glycol is least. The solubility behavior and chemical resistance of the membrane has also been studied and the membrane is found to be resistant to water, acid and bases.

Keywords : Template polymerization, membrane, absorption, chemical resistance, solubility, viscosity.

Introduction

Template polymerization (matrix or replica polymerization) is related to the general field of polymerization catalysis. In template polymerization¹, we seek to achieve polymerization of monomer units attached to a template in a predetermined manner and thus to synthesize polymers or copolymers having precise structures and microstructures complementary of those of the template.

The outstanding characteristics of template polymerization are as follows :

(i) Complex formation which takes place between two polymers, as has been shown on the basis of various physicochemical techniques²⁻⁵.

(ii) The rate of polymerization increases as the concentration of template increases. The enhancement in rate is due to decrease in termination rate constant⁶.

(iii) The structural and conformational features of the template are reflected in the corresponding daughter polymers.

A search of literature⁷⁻¹³ reveals that almost all reports on template polymerization have been published in connection with the homo polymerization or co-polymerization of vinyl monomers and there are few reports¹⁴ on the synthesis of polymeric membrane in the presence of template through template polymerization. Bechold

*et al.*¹⁵ prepared the first series of membranes of graded porosities and was the first to functionally characterize the polymeric membrane by well defined permeability measurement in which the pressure required to blow air through a water filled capillary. The permeation process consists absorption of the components of the liquid into membrane, their transport by molecular diffusion through it and evaporation at the membrane surface^{16,17}.

The present communication provides a detailed investigation on the behaviour of poly methyl methacrylate membrane towards chemical solubility, chemical resistance, chemical absorption and its viscometric measurements.

Experimental

Purification methods :

Vinyl acetate was purified¹⁸ by double distillation at atmospheric pressure. The fraction boiling in the range of 72 °C was collected. Methyl methacrylate (MMA) was distilled under reduced pressure and purified according to the method of Overberger¹⁹. The initiator benzoyl peroxide was purified by dissolving it in chloroform before use²⁰.

Preparation of template :

The polyvinyl acetate template was prepared by the polymerization of vinyl acetate (3.6 mol L⁻¹) in benzene at 60 °C in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen, ben-

zoyle peroxide ($4.12 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$) was used as the initiator. After four hours, the polymerization was completed and the polymer was precipitated in distilled water. The formed polymer was dried, redissolved in acetone and reprecipitated in *n*-hexane.

Characterisation of the template :

In NMR spectrum of polymer (Fig. 1), the methoxy protons appear as a singlet at τ 5.91 the methyl protons and methylene protons appear as triplet in the range of τ 8.5–9.0 and τ 7.5–8.5 respectively. The appearance of methoxy protons as a single peak shows that the formed polymer is random in nature.

polymerization was performed in a test tube under an inert atmosphere of nitrogen gas at $60 \pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for three hours in a thermostat water bath.

The glass plates ($12'' \times 5'' \times 3/16''$) used for casting the PMMA membrane were treated with the mixture of concentrated sulphuric acid and potassium dichromate then washed and rinsed with distilled water and dried in an oven at $60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for an hour. The membrane was then casted by pouring the concentrated solution on the clean dry glass plate and tilting it back and forth to spread the solution on to the glass plate uniformly. The membranes were kept at room temperature for two days for drying purpose. The composition of PMMA membrane are given in Table 1.

Fig. 1. NMR spectrum of template (PVAc).

Preparation and casting of PMMA membrane :

The poly methyl methacrylate (PMMA) membrane was prepared by dissolving poly vinyl acetate (PVAc) in dimethyl formamide (DMF) with constant stirring for an hour. When the polymer gets completely dissolved, then α, α' -azo bis isobutyronitrile and MMA were added to it and again stirred for an hour. The

The intrinsic viscosity (η) and specific viscosity (η_{sp}) was calculated by the following relationships

$$\eta_{sp} = \frac{t - t_0}{t_0}$$

$$[\eta] (\text{dl.g}^{-1}) = (\eta_{sp} / \text{conc.})^{\text{conc}} = 0$$

Table 1. Composition of PMMA membrane

Membrane code	Membrane composition						
	[PVAc] (mol L ⁻¹)	[MMA] (mol L ⁻¹)	[AIBN] × 10 ² (mol L ⁻¹)	[DMF] (ml)	[Toluene] (ml)	Temp. (°C)	Time (min)
PM1	3.25	1.76	3.98	15	–	60	180
PM2	2.76	1.76	3.98	15	–	60	180
PM3	1.61	1.76	3.98	15	–	60	180
PM4	3.25	1.76	3.98	15	0.6	60	180
PM5	3.25	1.76	3.98	15	1.0	60	180

The efflux time (s) of pure solvent (t_0) and solution (t) of different concentrations (0.4, 0.3, 0.2, 0.1%) of polymer in solvent was determined with the help of Ubbelohde viscometer. The intrinsic viscosity $[\eta]$ was computed by extrapolating a plot of η_{sp} versus concentration of zero concentration.

Results and discussion

Absorption experiment :

Absorption implies the penetration of a liquid into the body of the solid. The absorptive nature of PMMA membrane has been investigated by using water, ethylene glycol, *n*-hexane and cyclohexane as test liquids. The equilibrium absorption of cyclohexane-ethylene glycol obtained from solubility experiments are 3.0 and 0.64 mg at 40 °C, respectively in polymeric membrane 1 (PM1). The behaviour of binary mixture of cyclohexane-ethylene glycol on polymethyl methacrylate membrane has been demonstrated in Fig. 2. It is clear from the figure that the absorption increases with increase in the concentration of cyclohexane-ethylene glycol mixture decreases with decreasing the concentration of poly vinyl acetate template in the membrane. A study of Fig. 3 reveals that the absorption of water in membrane was highest while hexane and cyclohexane also exhibited high absorption, but the absorption of ethylene glycol was relatively low. The relatively lower absorption of hexane, cyclohexane and ethylene glycol in comparison to water is in agreement with lesser solubility parameters.

The role of temperature on the absorption in the membrane has been presented in Fig. 4 in presence of cyclohexane, ethylene glycol at 40 °C and 60 °C, respectively. The amount of absorption is not affected by the variation in the concentration of the template, but the absorption increases as the temperature increases.

Solubility and chemical resistance :

Solubility implies when a solid or liquid dissolves,

the structural units (ions/molecule) becomes separated from each other and the space in between is occupied by solvent molecule. As listed in Table 2, the effect of various inorganic and organic solvents were used to check the solubility behaviour of polymeric membrane. The data showed that the polymeric membrane was soluble in various strong organic solvents. It is probably because the membrane molecules are huge (high molecular weight) molecules as compared to the solvent molecules, they

Fig. 2. Amount absorbed by different compositions of poly MMA membranes : (i) in binary solvent cyclohexane-ethylene glycol for PM₁ (▲) ; PM₂ (■) and PM₃ (●); (ii) in water for PM₁ (○); PM₂ (◻) and PM₃ (△). As a function of time at 40 °C.

Fig. 3. Amount absorbed of poly MMA membrane, from solvents as a function of time at 40 °C. Absorption of water (○), cyclohexane (◻), hexane (△) and ethylene glycol (●).

Fig. 4. Amount absorbed of poly MMA membrane, from cyclohexane ethylene-glycol mixture as a function of time at 60 °C (○) and at 40 °C (●).

swell considerably in volume during the process of dissolution. The giant size and the increase in volume of polymer molecule restrict its molecular mobility in the solution and increases the inter molecular friction. The

Table 2. Solubility of polymethyl methacrylate membrane

Sl. no.	Solvent	Polymer membrane ^a		
		PM1	PM2	PM3
1.	H ₂ SO ₄	-	-	-
2.	HCl	-	-	-
3.	HNO ₃	++	++	++
4.	CH ₃ COOH	-	-	-
5.	NaOH	-	-	-
6.	NH ₄ OH	-	-	-
7.	CCl ₄	-	-	-
8.	Benzene	++	++	++
9.	Toluene	++	++	++
10.	Dimethyl formamide	++	++	++
11.	Dimethyl sulfoxide	++	++	++
12.	Dioxane	++	++	++
13.	Diethyl ether	-	+	++
14.	Methanol	++	++	++
15.	Water	-	-	-
16.	Dichloro methane	++	++	++

^a ++ = Soluble at room temperature.
 + = Soluble on heating (40 °C).
 - = Insoluble.

insolubility of membrane in concentrated sulphuric acid, concentrated hydrochloric acid, sodium hydroxide, ammonium hydroxide, carbon tetrachloride and water is due to absorption of these solvents, a strong interaction is formed on the surface of the membrane which does not permit the solvent to transport through the membrane.

Viscometric measurements for complex formation :

The template system methyl methacrylate/poly vinyl acetate, has been investigated by means of viscometric techniques. In order to investigate the complexation between poly vinyl acetate and poly methyl methacrylate, the polymers were dissolved separately in DMF and mixed just before the measurements. The viscometric measurements were carried out at 35 ± 0.1 °C. The variation in the reduced viscosity ($\eta_{red.} = \eta_{sp}/C$) of the PVAc/PMMA mixture in DMF as a function of composition is shown in Fig. 5. The maximum complexation corresponds to 1 : 1 molar ratio where complexation is very fast in Fig. 6 and there is a rapid decrease within 10 min down to a level that remains constant. This indicates that complexation is virtually completed within 10 min. Early reports regarding time needed for complex formation during template polymerization also supports it²¹⁻²³.

Fig. 5. Reduced viscosity (η_{sp}/C) as a function of weight percent of PVAc for at-PVAc/PMMA mixture in DMF, during the polymerization of MMA.

Fig. 6. Reduced viscosity (η_{sp}/C) as a function of time of PVAc for PVAc/PMMA mixture in DMF during the polymerization of MMA.

Conclusion :

From these studies we infer that the template polymerization of PMMA using PVAc shows that the time required for complete complex formation is generally 10 min. The absorption of water in the film was highest, while cyclohexane also exhibited high absorption, but absorption of hexane and ethylene glycol was relatively low. The membrane was resistant to water, acids and bases and was insoluble in organic solvents.

References

1. A. K. Srivastava, S. K. Nigam, A. K. Shukla, S. Saini, P. Kumar and N. J. Tewari, *Macromol. Sci. - Rev. Macromol. Chem. Phys.*, 1987, **C22**, 171.
2. H. Z. Liu and K. I. Liu, *Macromolecules*, 1968, **1**, 157.
3. J. Smid, Y. Y. Tan and G. Challa, *Polymer Commun.*, 1986, **27**, 148.
4. E. L. Feitsma, A. De Boer and G. Challa, *Polymer*, 1975, **16**, 515.
5. J. Dayantis, C. Reiss and H. Benoit, *Makromol. Chemie*, 1968, **120**, 113.
6. K. Fujimori, *Makromol. Chemie*, 1979, **180**, 1743.
7. Daniele Semino, Giovanni Polacco and Ricciardi Alessandra, *Polym. Sci. Engg.*, 1997, **37**, 1404.
8. M. Kalagasidis and E. D. Krusi, *Unuzovi European Polymer J.*, 2004, **40**, 793.
9. Reiko Saito, Yoshiki Okuno and Hiroaki Kobayashi, *J. Polym. Sci., Part A. Polym. Chem.*, 2001, **39**, 3539.
10. S. K. Saha and S. Bhattacharya, *J. Appl. Phys. Lett.*, 2002, **80**, 4612.
11. Ciardlli Gianluca, *Polymer International*, 2001, **50**, 588.
12. A. Charalambopoulou, G. Bokias and G. Staikos, *Polymer Journal*, 2002, **43**, 2637.
13. Reiko Saito and Hiroaki Kobayashi, *Macromolecules*, 2002, **35**, 7207.
14. T. Fukutorni, A. Yokota and K. Ishizu, *J. Polym. Sci., Polymer Chem. Ed.*, 1982, **20**, 619.
15. Z. Bechold, *Physik Chem.*, 1907, **60**, 257.
16. R. Y. M. Huang and V. J. C. Lin, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 1968, **12**, 2615.
17. I. Cabasso, J. Jagur-Crodzinski and D. Vofsi, *J. Appl. Polym.*, 1974, **18**, 2117.
18. D. H. Napper and A. C. Parts, *J. Polym. Sci.*, 1962, **61**, 113.
19. C. G. Overberger and N. Yamamoto, *J. Polym. Sci., Polym. Chem. Ed.*, 1965, **4**, 101.
20. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", Longmann, London, 1956, p. 172.
21. J. Smid, Y. Y. Tan and G. Challa, *Polymer Commun.*, 1986, **27**, 148.
22. J. Matuszewska-Czerwik and S. Polowinski, *Polymer Bull.*, 1988, **19**, 149.
23. J. Gons, E. J. Vorenkamp and G. Challa, *J. Polym. Sci., Polym. Chem. Ed.*, 1977, **15**, 3031.